

Diagnostic Delay, Psychosocial Burden and Treatment Expectations in 100 Patients with Lipedema: A Cross-Sectional Observational Study

Luisella Rosa Anna Troyer ¹, Giorgio Fiorini ², *

¹ Salus Mea Medical Studio, Via Padova 95 – 20127 Milan, Italy: luisella.troyer@milanolinfedema.it

² Salus Mea Medical Studio, Via Padova 95 – 20127 Milan, Italy: giorgio.fiorini@milanolinfedema.it

* Correspondence: giorgio.fiorini@milanolinfedema.it; Tel. +39 3388309945

Abstract

Background/Objectives: Lipedema is a chronic adipose tissue disorder predominantly affecting females, characterized by symmetrical, painful accumulation of fatty tissue in the lower limbs and often the arms. Despite its estimated high prevalence, it remains systematically underdiagnosed in Italy. This study describes the clinical, demographic, psychological, and therapeutic characteristics of 100 patients referred to a specialist center, focusing on diagnostic delay and its impact on quality of life. **Methods:** Cross-sectional observational study using a structured questionnaire (18 items) administered to 100 consecutive female patients (mean age 35.2 years; range 18–58) at the Salus Mea outpatient clinic of Dr. Luisella Troyer between September 2023 and January 2026. The questionnaire covered demographics, onset, clinical symptoms, previous treatments, psychological impact, and willingness to undergo treatment. In accordance with Italian regulations on non-interventional observational studies involving anonymized data (Determina AIFA 2008; D.Lgs. 211/2003), formal ethics committee approval was not required. All participants provided informed consent; data were processed in GDPR compliance (EU 2016/679). **Results:** 85% of patients had no previous diagnosis; 63% discovered the condition independently online. 91% present spontaneous bruising; 76% report pain on palpation. 77% exhibit body-avoidance behaviors in public; 59.6% report frequent sadness, melancholy, or anger. 89% declare willingness to undergo specific treatment; 65% are tentatively willing to undergo surgery. **Conclusions:** The data confirm severe, systematic diagnostic delay of lipedema in the Italian healthcare context, with significant psychosocial impact on quality of life. The near-universal treatment willingness reflects an unmet therapeutic need requiring urgent responses from the healthcare system.

Keywords: lipedema; diagnostic delay; quality of life; psychological impact; observational study; lymphology; vascular surgery

1. Introduction

Lipedema is a chronic, progressive and typically female condition characterized by bilateral and symmetrical accumulation of pathological adipose tissue in the lower limbs and, frequently, the arms.

First described by Allen and Hines in 1940 [1], the condition remains widely underdiagnosed today, with prevalence estimates ranging from 1% to 11% of the adult female population in Western countries [2,3].

The pathophysiology of lipedema is not yet fully understood: the most widely accepted hypotheses suggest a genetic origin with variable penetrance, modulated by

hormonal factors—particularly estrogens—which would explain the frequent onset at significant hormonal events such as puberty, pregnancy, menopause, fertility treatments and hormonal therapies.

The presence of lipedema in male subjects (a minority of less than 2% of known cases) has been observed in patients who already exhibited hormonal problems and/or imbalances, supporting the hypothesis that the genetic command activating the dysmorphic distribution of the adipose panniculus is mediated by hormonal activity.

At the histological level, alterations of the microcirculation, fibrosis of the adipose tissue and, not infrequently, lymphatic damage are observed, resulting in chronic pain, oedema and capillary fragility [4,5].

The consequences of this underdiagnosis are not solely clinical: numerous studies show that patients with lipedema present significantly elevated rates of depression, anxiety, low self-esteem and reduced health-related quality of life [6,7,8,9].

Clinically, lipedema is distinguished from common obesity and lymphoedema by several distinctive features: symmetrical distribution sparing the feet and hands; presence of pain and increased sensitivity on palpation; tendency to form spontaneous bruising; and resistance to weight loss through diet and physical activity.

Despite these clinically identifiable features, the condition remains largely unrecognized in everyday medical practice, with a mean diagnostic delay reported to exceed 10 years in most studies [10,11].

In Italy, specific epidemiological data on lipedema remain scarce and healthcare professionals' training on the condition is inadequate. The present study is set within this context, with the aim of providing systematic observational data on an Italian sample of 100 consecutive patients who attended the Salus Mea medical practice of Dr. Luisella Troyer as first-access referrals with a suspected or confirmed diagnosis of lipedema.

The specific objectives of the study were:

- Describe the demographic and clinical characteristics of the sample.
- Quantify the diagnostic delay and the modalities through which the condition was discovered.
- Characterize the main clinical symptoms, with attention to bruising and pain on palpation.
- Assess the psychological and relational impact of the condition.
- Explore expectations and willingness to undergo treatment.

2. Materials and Methods

This is a cross-sectional observational study conducted on one hundred female patients attending the Salus Mea specialist outpatient clinic of Dr. Luisella Troyer between September 2023 and January 2026. All the patients, during the specified period, underwent a specialist consultation for suspected or previously diagnosed lipedema were included in the study. Sampling is convenience-based (consecutive patients): no exclusion criteria were applied regarding age, body weight or the presence of comorbidities, in order to obtain a realistic representation of the population attending the center. All participants provided informed consent for data processing in accordance with the GDPR (EU Regulation 2016/679).

A structured questionnaire comprising 18 closed- and open-ended questions was administered, organized into the following sections:

- Demographic and anthropometric data (age, height, weight)
- Diagnosis and modality of discovering the condition
- Onset and development of lipedema
- Clinical symptoms (bruising, pain on palpation)
- Previous treatments and perceived efficacy
- Psychological and relational impact
- Willingness to undergo medical and surgical treatments

The questionnaire was administered digitally via an online form prior to the specialist consultation, enabling autonomous completion by the patient. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Categorical variables are expressed as absolute frequencies (n) and percentages (%). Continuous variables (age, height, weight) are expressed as arithmetic mean and range (min–max).

Missing responses were present in the following variables: intimacy with partner (n = 1), public avoidance (n = 1), and frequency of sadness, melancholy or anger related to physical condition (n = 1). These were excluded from the percentage calculation for each variable and noted in the respective tables.

Data were processed using the Python library `Pandas` (version 2.0).

3. Results

3.1. Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

The sample comprises 100 female patients. Anthropometric characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic and anthropometric characteristics of the sample (N = 100).

Variable	Value
Number of patients	100
Sex	100% female
Age – Mean (years)	35.2

Age – Range (years)	18–58
Height – Mean (cm)	164.9
Height – Range (cm)	146–181
Weight – Mean (kg)	69.9
Weight – Range (kg)	48–110
Data collection period	September 2023–January 2026
GDPR consent	100% (100/100)

The sample shows wide weight variability (48–110 kg), confirming the need not to automatically associate lipedema with obesity. The mean weight of 69.9 kg reinforces that lipedema is not an overweight condition. 111
112
113

3.2. Diagnosis and Diagnostic Delay 114

Table 2 summarizes whether patients had previously received a lipedema diagnosis. 115

Table 2. Previous diagnosis of lipedema (N = 100). 116

Question	Response	N	%
Have you been previously diagnosed with lipedema?	No	85	85%
	Yes	15	15%

¹ Critical data: 85% of patients had never received a diagnosis of lipedema prior to attending the specialist center. This finding testifies to a serious diagnostic gap in the Italian healthcare system. 117
118
119

Table 3 illustrates the modalities through which patients came to learn about their condition. 120
121

Table 3. Modality of lipedema discovery (N = 100). 122

Question	Response	N	%
How did you learn about lipedema?	I researched it online	37	37%
	I discovered it by chance online	26	26%
	Diagnosed by a physician	14	14%
	Suggestion by beautician/masseuse	14	14%
	Advice from a friend with lipedema	4	4%
	Diagnosed by a physiotherapist	3	3%
	Dr. Troyer's website	2	2%

¹ Interpretation: the diagnostic role of the formal healthcare system appears wholly inadequate. The high proportion of Internet-mediated self-diagnosis raises important questions about the training of health professionals regarding lipedema. 123
124
125

The most significant finding is that 63% of the sample discovered their condition through the Internet: 37% by actively researching it, 26% by chance. Only 14% received a diagnosis from a physician. Notably, a beautician or masseuse directed patients towards a diagnosis at the same rate as physicians (14% vs. 14%). 126
127
128
129

3.3. Onset of Lipedema

Table 4 shows the perceived age of lipedema onset as reported by patients.

Table 4. Perceived age of lipedema onset (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
At what age do you think lipedema began to develop?	From puberty onwards	43	43%
	In adulthood	22	22%
	I don't know / I feel I've always had it	18	18%
	Since childhood	12	12%
	After hormonal treatment	2	2%
	After pregnancy and childbirth	2	2%
	After menopause	1	1%

¹ Clinical note: the role of estrogens in the activation of lipedema is further supported by patients with onset after hormonal treatment (2%), after pregnancy (2%) and after menopause (1%), totaling 5% with an identifiable hormonal trigger.

43% of patients report onset at puberty; 18% report feeling they have always had it. 12% identify onset in childhood. Assuming that the response group 'I don't know / I feel I've always had it' may be interpreted as recollection of a pubertal or pre-pubertal condition, 73% of the sample place onset at pubertal or pre-pubertal age, reinforcing the hypothesis of an activation correlated with female hormonal events.

3.4. Main Clinical Symptoms

3.4.1. Spontaneous Bruising

Table 5 presents the frequency of spontaneous bruising in the lower limbs and arms.

Table 5. Appearance of spontaneous bruising on lower limbs and arms (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
Do you often get bruises on your lower limbs and arms that you can't remember the cause of?	Yes, occasionally	68	68%
	Yes, constantly	23	23%
	No, never	9	9%

¹ Clinical proposal: the presence of spontaneous bruising in the lower limb region in female subjects may be considered as a potential diagnostic indicator requiring validation in prospective studies for lipedema, even in the absence of a formal diagnosis.

91% of the sample reports the appearance of spontaneous bruising in the arms and lower limbs. This finding has significant clinical relevance: the tendency to spontaneous bruising reflects the microvascular damage caused by the increased mechanical pressure exerted by the pathological adipose panniculus on the superficial venous microcirculation.

3.4.2. Pain on Palpation

Table 6 shows the distribution of pain intensity on palpation of arms and lower limbs.

Table 6. Pain on palpation of arms and lower limbs (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
Do your arms and lower limbs hurt when you are touched or felt?	Moderate pain	37	37%
	Mild pain	30	30%
	Absent	24	24%
	Intense pain	9	9%

76% of patients report pain on palpation of the limbs, with moderate pain predominating (37%). Pain on palpation represents one of the distinctive symptoms of lipedema and helps to differentiate it from common obesity. The 24% of patients with no pain on palpation may reflect an early stage of the condition or individual variability in pain perception.

3.5. Previous Treatments

Table 7 summarizes previous treatments for lipedema reported by patients.

Table 7. Previous treatments for lipedema (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
Have you had any treatment for lipedema in the past?	No treatment	68	68%
	Massage and bandaging	15	15%
	Specific medical treatment	8	8%
	Liposuction	7	7%
	Topical creams	2	2%

68% of the sample has never undergone any specific treatment for lipedema, a finding consistent with the high prevalence of prior undiagnosed cases. The 32 patients who had received treatment report predominantly unsatisfactory results (Table 8).

Table 8. Perceived efficacy of previous treatments (N = 32).

Question	Response	N	%
If so, can you tell the Doctor the result of this treatment?	Almost useless	10	31.3%
	Mediocre	10	31.3%
	Poor	5	15.6%
	Good	5	15.6%
	Satisfactory	2	6.3%

¹ Critical data: 78.1% of treated patients (poor + mediocre + almost useless) did not obtain clinically relevant benefit from the treatments received. This finding, read together with the prevalence of undiagnosed cases, suggests that many treatments were undertaken without a correct identification of the condition, inevitably proving ineffective.

3.6. Psychological and Relational Impact

3.6.1 Mood and Psychological Distress

Table 9 reports the frequency of sadness, melancholy or anger related to the physical condition.

Table 9. Frequency of sadness, melancholy or anger related to physical condition (N = 100; 1 missing response).

Question	Response	N	%
Do you often feel sad, melancholic, angry about the condition of your legs?	Constantly	33	33.3%
	Quite often	26	26.3%
	Sometimes	18	18.2%
	Rarely	14	14.1%
	Never	8	8.1%
	Missing response	1	-

59.6% of the sample (constantly + quite often) reports frequent feelings of sadness, melancholy or anger related to their physical condition; 33% describe this distress as constant. Broadening the definition to any degree of reported distress (including 'sometimes'), the prevalence rises to 77%.

3.6.2. Avoidance Behavior

Table 10 reports on avoidance of exposing legs or arms in public.

Table 10. Avoidance of exposing legs or arms in public (N = 99; 1 missing response).

Question	Response	N	%
Do you avoid showing your legs or arms in public?	Constantly	40	40.4%
	Quite often	21	21.2%
	Sometimes	16	16.2%
	Rarely	12	12.1%
	Never	10	10.1%
	Missing response	1	-

77.8% of patients avoid exposing their legs or arms in public (constantly + quite often + sometimes), with 40% doing so systematically and constantly. This avoidance behavior is indicative of a marked impairment of body image, with direct repercussions on social life.

3.6.3. Interpersonal Relationships and Intimacy

Table 11 shows the impact of lipedema on interpersonal and affective relationships.

Table 11. Impact on interpersonal/affective relationships (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
Does your condition affect your interpersonal or emotional relationships?	No, not at all	31	31%
	Yes, but not much	23	23%
	Yes, sometimes	21	21%
	Yes, quite a lot	15	15%
	Yes, constantly	10	10%

69% of the sample acknowledges an impact on their relational and affective life. Considering only the most significant degrees (quite a lot + constantly), the prevalence is 25%. Only 31% perceive no relational impairment.

Table 11.1. Intimacy with partner (N = 99; 1 missing response).

Question	Response	N	%
When it comes to intimacy with your partner/husband, do you often feel inadequate?	No, not at all	40	40.4%
	Yes, but not much	23	23.2%
	Yes, sometimes	18	18.2%
	Yes, quite a lot	10	10.1%
	Yes, constantly	8	8.1%
	Missing response	1	-

Regarding intimacy with a partner, 59.6% report feelings of inadequacy of any intensity.

3.6.4. Body dissatisfaction or appearance-related comparison and Sense of Injustice

Table 12. Body dissatisfaction or appearance-related comparison for other women's bodies (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
Do you sometimes find yourself feeling, even without wanting to, envious of other women's bodies, to the point of being surprised by them?	Sometimes	23	23%
	Constantly	26	26%
	Quite a lot	21	21%
	Yes, but not much	14	14%
	No, not at all	16	16%

84% of patients report involuntarily feeling envious of other women's bodies (26% constantly), when broadening the definition to any degree of reported distress, including 'sometimes'.

Table 12.1. Sense of injustice regarding physical condition (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
Do you often think that your physical condition is unfair, and that it should be changed?	No, not at all	8	8%
	Yes, but not much	15	15%
	Yes, sometimes	26	26%
	Yes, quite a lot	20	20%
	Yes, constantly	31	31%

92% consider their physical condition unjust and in need of change (31% constantly, 26% sometimes).

3.7. Expectations and Willingness to Undergo Treatment

3.7.1. Willingness to Undergo Medical Treatment

Table 13 shows patients' willingness to undergo specific, lengthy and demanding treatments.

Table 13. Willingness to undergo specific, lengthy and demanding treatments (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
If Dr. Troyer suggested a specific treatment for your condition, but it was long and demanding, would you be willing to follow it?			58%
	Yes, but I would think carefully first	58	
	Yes, totally willing	31	31%
	No, but I could change my mind	10	10%
	No, definitely not	1	1%

89% of patients declare willingness, at various levels, to undertake specific treatments, even if lengthy and demanding, highlighting an unmet therapeutic need of very large dimensions.

3.7.2. Willingness to Undergo Surgery

Table 14 presents patients' willingness to undergo surgical lipedema reduction.

Table 14. Willingness to undergo surgical lipedema reduction (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
If there were a clinical indication, would you be available for surgery to reduce lipedema?	Yes, but I would need to think about it	29	29%
	Yes, totally willing	21	21%
	Tentatively yes, but I would want guarantees	15	15%
	No, but I could change my mind	22	22%
	No, definitely not	13	13%

65% of patients express a tentatively favorable position towards surgery (totally willing 21% + would need to think 29% + would want guarantees 15%), while 13% categorically exclude it. 22% do not exclude surgery but require further deliberation.

3.8. Diet and Lipedema

Table 15. Patients currently following a specific diet (N = 100).

Question	Response	N	%
Are you currently following a specific diet?	No	63	63%
	Yes	37	37%

63% of patients are not currently following a specific diet; 37% are. This finding is particularly relevant: lipedema does not respond to dietary restrictions in a manner

comparable to common obesity, and dietary therapy cannot be used as a treatment for the reduction of pathological adipose tissue distribution.

4. Discussion

The present study provides a detailed clinical and psychosocial characterization of an Italian cohort of 100 patients with lipedema and highlights several findings of substantial clinical relevance. In particular, the data draw attention to three closely connected issues: marked diagnostic delay, a considerable psychological burden, and the persistent under-recognition of lipedema within the Italian healthcare setting. This focus is especially relevant in light of the limited Italian literature currently available. Notably, the largest recent Italian observational study, conducted by Patton et al. [12] on 360 women, explicitly stated that no previous study had reported data on Italian women with lipedema; however, that work was primarily centered on clinical, instrumental, and biochemical characterization rather than on the diagnostic journey and psychosocial experience of patients. In this respect, the present study adds a distinct and complementary perspective to the emerging national literature.

The most striking finding of the present study is the extent of diagnostic delay. The fact that 85% of patients had never received a diagnosis of lipedema before referral to the specialist center strongly suggests that the disease remains insufficiently recognized in routine clinical practice. This finding is consistent with international literature showing that underdiagnosis is a major problem in lipedema, but the magnitude observed in our cohort appears particularly concerning. In the Dutch survey by Romeijn et al. [13], the mean time from symptom onset to diagnosis was 18 years, while the Swedish national survey by Falck et al. [14] similarly concluded that many women with lipedema remain underdiagnosed and unsupported by healthcare services. Our data therefore align with previous international evidence, while suggesting that the diagnostic gap may be especially pronounced in Italy.

Against this background, it is not surprising that 63% of patients reported relying on the Internet to understand their condition. Equally telling is the observation that beauticians directed patients toward a diagnosis as often as physicians. Although this finding arises from patient self-report, it is nevertheless clinically and culturally meaningful, as it reflects a gap in professional awareness among healthcare providers who are more likely to encounter the early manifestations of the disease in everyday practice. Qualitative evidence from other settings points in the same direction: women with lipedema frequently report stigmatizing or dismissive encounters with healthcare providers, diagnostic confusion with obesity, and prolonged uncertainty before receiving an explanation for their symptoms. Taken together, these observations support the need for targeted educational initiatives for general practitioners and for specialists who commonly evaluate women with weight, endocrine, gynecologic, or vascular complaints.

The clinical findings of our study are also broadly consistent with the existing literature. Spontaneous or minimal-trauma bruising was reported by 91% of patients, while pain on palpation was present in 76%. Both symptoms are well-established clinical features of lipedema and have been reported at high prevalence in previous observational studies. Romeijn et al. [13] identified pain and easy bruising as the leading complaints in their survey cohort, and the large Italian study by Patton et al. [12] likewise found bruising due to minimal trauma or occurring spontaneously in 80.8% of cases, with pain on pinching among the most frequent clinical signs. The particularly high prevalence of

bruising in our sample reinforces the view that this feature may represent a practical and accessible diagnostic clue in everyday clinical assessment, especially when present in a characteristic distribution and in the absence of alternative explanations.

The timing of symptom onset observed in our cohort further supports current pathogenetic models. The frequent onset at puberty, together with reports of childhood onset and hormonally related worsening, is coherent with the widely accepted view that lipedema often emerges or becomes clinically apparent during phases of hormonal change, including puberty, pregnancy, and menopause. Although the precise pathophysiology remains incompletely understood, recent literature continues to support a role for estrogen-related mechanisms acting on a genetically predisposed background. Our findings are therefore in line with current conceptual models of disease onset and progression.

One of the most important contributions of the present study concerns the psychological dimension of lipedema. The high prevalence of body exposure avoidance, dissatisfaction with one's body, depressive feelings or anger, and impairment in affective life clearly indicates that lipedema cannot be interpreted as a disorder limited to adipose tissue distribution and pain. Rather, it should be understood as a chronic condition with major consequences for self-image, intimate relationships, and emotional well-being. This interpretation is strongly supported by the literature. Hamatschek et al. [15], using both a lipedema-specific questionnaire and validated instruments such as the WHOQOL-BREF and PHQ-9, documented a high level of mental stress in a large cohort of patients. In a case-control study, Al-Wardat et al. [16] found significantly greater anxiety and more severe difficulties in emotional regulation among women with lipedema than among healthy controls, even after adjustment for BMI. Similarly, Kempa et al. [17] reported a higher prevalence and severity of depressive symptoms in patients with lipedema and showed that pain severity correlated positively with depressive symptoms and impaired health-related quality of life. Our results are fully consistent with this line of evidence and further emphasize that psychological suffering is not a secondary or marginal feature of the disease.

The impact on relational and intimate life deserves particular attention. In our cohort, a large proportion of patients reported difficulties in affective life and feelings of inadequacy in intimacy with their partner. These findings resonate with qualitative data showing that shame, stigma, and altered self-confidence may profoundly affect social participation and romantic relationships, particularly in younger women. Thus, the psychosocial burden associated with lipedema appears to extend beyond generic distress and to affect highly personal and relational aspects of life that are rarely explored in routine clinical assessment. This is one of the areas in which the present study adds granularity to the existing literature, since many previous studies have emphasized quality of life or depressive symptoms but have explored intimate and affective functioning in less detail.

Our findings on treatment are equally relevant. The fact that 68% of patients had never received any specific treatment is understandable in the context of absent or delayed diagnosis. More concerning, however, is that even among previously treated patients, most reported unsatisfactory outcomes. This pattern suggests not only limited access to care, but also a lack of consistent and effective treatment pathways. Recent literature confirms that management remains challenging: Falck et al. [14] noted that women with lipedema are often left without adequate support from healthcare systems,

and their later mixed-methods study [18] emphasized that women frequently face fragmented care, rely heavily on self-management, and encounter considerable uncertainty regarding available treatments. At the same time, the high willingness to undergo both conservative and surgical treatment observed in our cohort points to a substantial unmet therapeutic need. Patients are actively seeking care, but the healthcare system appears insufficiently prepared to provide timely diagnosis, structured counseling, and evidence-informed treatment options.

From the perspective of the literature, the novelty of the present study lies less in documenting isolated symptoms that are already known, and more in capturing their convergence within the Italian clinical context. Compared with prior international surveys, our findings confirm the recurring triad of pain, bruising, and reduced psychosocial well-being. Compared with the recent Italian work by Patton et al. [12], however, our study shifts the emphasis from phenotypic and instrumental characterization toward the patient journey, specifically highlighting diagnostic invisibility, reliance on non-medical sources of information, dissatisfaction with care, and the burden on emotional and relational life. This focus is particularly relevant in a country where national data remain scarce and where the under-recognition of lipedema appears to persist despite increasing scientific attention.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, this was a convenience sample recruited at a single specialist center, which may have enriched the cohort for patients with more severe symptoms, greater distress, or higher disease awareness. Second, the analysis was based on self-reported information, with the inherent risk of recall bias, particularly for age at onset, prior treatment history, and pathways to diagnosis. Third, the questionnaire did not include validated quality-of-life or psychiatric instruments, which limits direct comparability with studies using standardized tools such as the RAND-36, EQ-5D, WHOQOL-BREF, or PHQ-9. Finally, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inference, and the absence of objective staging data prevents a more refined analysis of how symptom burden varies according to disease severity. These limitations notwithstanding, the inclusion of 100 consecutive patients, the systematic data collection, and the specific attention to diagnostic and psychosocial aspects provide meaningful descriptive value and fill an important gap in the Italian literature.

Overall, our findings support a clear clinical implication: earlier recognition of lipedema is likely to reduce inappropriate weight-loss approaches, shorten the path to diagnosis, and improve referral to multidisciplinary care. Just as importantly, the results indicate that psychological support should not be considered optional, but rather an integral part of care. In the Italian context, where lipedema still appears to be under-recognized, these data may help inform future diagnostic training initiatives, patient pathways, and intervention studies.

5. Conclusions

The results of the present observational study on 100 patients with lipedema allow several conclusions of clinical and public health relevance to be drawn.

Diagnostic delay is the most urgent issue: 85% of patients had never received an adequate diagnosis, and 63% had to rely on the Internet to understand their condition. This scenario reflects a systemic Italian training gap that requires urgent and targeted interventions.

The clinical symptoms of lipedema—pain on palpation (76%), spontaneous bruising (91%)—were confirmed at high prevalence. The presence of spontaneous bruising emerges as a potentially accessible and straightforward diagnostic marker.

The psychological impact is of great relevance: 59.6% report frequent states of sadness or anger, 77% avoid showing their body in public, 69% report impairment of their affective life. These data call for a multidisciplinary approach that includes structured psychological support.

The efficacy of treatments received was very low (78.1% unsatisfactory outcomes among treated patients). Willingness to undergo treatment (89% for medical treatments, 65% favorable to surgery) documents an unmet therapeutic need of great magnitude.

In summary, lipedema in Italy represents a condition that is under-recognized, undertreated and underestimated in its psychological dimension. This study contributes to filling a gap in the national literature and provides baseline data for future intervention research.

Supplementary Materials: Non applicable

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, L.T. and G.F.; methodology, L.T. and G.F.; investigation, L.T.; data curation, G.F.; formal analysis, G.F.; writing—original draft preparation, G.F.; writing—review and editing, L.T. and G.F.; supervision, L.T. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding. The study was funded with the authors' own resources. The APC was funded by the authors.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Ethical review and approval were waived for this study in accordance with Italian legislation on non-interventional observational studies (Determina AIFA 2008; D.Lgs. 211/2003), which does not require formal ethics committee approval for studies involving collection of anonymized self-reported questionnaire data without any clinical intervention. All participants provided informed consent for data processing in compliance with EU GDPR Regulation 2016/679.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author due to privacy and ethical restrictions relating to patient data.

Acknowledgments: The authors wish to thank all patients who participated in the study, agreeing to share sensitive information about their health condition.

We are grateful to Dr. Eleonora Villa for comments on the analysis of the aggregate data and for reading the draft.

Special thanks go to the secretarial staff of the Salus Mea medical practice for their support in data collection and management.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

- Allen EV, Hines EA Jr. Lipedema of the legs: a syndrome characterized by fat legs and orthostatic edema. *Proc Staff Meet Mayo Clin.* 1940;15:184–187.
- Herbst KL. Rare adipose disorders (RADs) masquerading as obesity.

- Acta Pharmacol Sin. 2012;33(2):155–172. 427
doi:10.1038/aps.2011.153 428
3. Kruppa P, Georgiou I, Biermann N, Prantl L, Klein-Weigel P, 429
Ghods M. Lipedema—Pathogenesis, Diagnosis, and Treatment Options. 430
Dtsch Arztebl Int. 2020;117(22-23):396–403. 431
doi:10.3238/arztebl.2020.0396 432
433
434
4. Child AH, Gordon KD, Sharpe P, Brice G, Ostergaard P, Jeffery S, 435
Mortimer PS. Lipedema: an inherited condition. Am J Med Genet A. 436
2010;152A(4):970–976. doi:10.1002/ajmg.a.33313 437
438
5. Forner-Cordero I, Szolnoky G, Forner-Cordero A, Kemény L. 439
Lipedema: an overview of its clinical manifestations, diagnosis and treatment of the disproportional fatty tissue deposition syn- 440
drome – systematic review. Clin Obes. 2012;2(3-4):86–95. 441
doi:10.1111/j.1758-8111.2012.00045.x 442
443
6. Dudek JE, Białaszek W, Gabriel M. Quality of life, its factors, and sociodemographic characteristics of Polish women with lipedema. 444
BMC Womens Health. 2021;21(1):27. 445
doi:10.1186/s12905-021-01174-y 446
447
7. Kruppa P, Biermann N, Cornely ME, Ghods M, Georgiou I, Prantl L, 448
Noah EM. Obesity and lipedema: differential diagnosis with liposuction. Plast Reconstr Surg. 2021;147(1):141e–152e. 449
doi:10.1097/PRS.00000000000007481 450
451
8. Buso G, Depairon M, Tomson D, Raffoul W, Vettor R, Mazzolai L. 452
Lipedema: A Call to Action! Obesity (Silver Spring). 453
2019;27(10):1567–1576. doi:10.1002/oby.22597 454
455
9. Dudek JE, Białaszek W, Ostaszewski P. Quality of life in women with lipoedema: a contextual behavioral model. Qual Life Res. 456
2016;25(2):401–408. doi:10.1007/s11136-015-1080-x 457
458
10. Bertsch T, Erbacher G. Lipoedema—misconceptions and facts. 459
Phlebologie. 2018;47(2):84–92. doi:10.12687/phleb2391-2-2018 460
461
11. Reich-Schupke S, Schmeller W, Brauer WJ, Cornely ME, Faerber G, Ludwig M, Lulay G, Miller A, Rapprich S, Richter DF, Schacht 462
V, Schrader K, Stücker M, Ure C. S1 guidelines: lipedema. J Dtsch 463
Dermatol Ges. 2017;15(7):758–767. doi:10.1111/ddg.13036 464
465
12. Patton L, Ricolfi L, Bortolon M, Gabriele G, Zolesio P, Cione E, 466
Cannataro R. Observational Study on a Large Italian Population with Lipedema: Biochemical and Hormonal Profile, Anatomical 467
and Clinical Evaluation, Self-Reported History. Int J Mol Sci. 468
2024;25(3):1599. doi:10.3390/ijms25031599 469
470
13. Romeijn JRM, de Rooij MJM, Janssen L, Martens H. Exploration 471
of Patient Characteristics and Quality of Life in Patients with Lipoedema Using a Survey. Dermatol Ther (Heidelb). 472
2018;8(2):303–311. doi:10.1007/s13555-018-0241-6 473
474
14. Falck J, Rolander B, Nygårdh A, Jonasson L, Mårtensson J. 475
Women with lipoedema: a national survey on their health, health-related quality of life, and sense of coherence. BMC 476
Womens Health. 2022;22(1):457. 477

- doi:10.1186/s12905-022-02022-3 478
- 479
15. Hamatschek M, Knors H, Klietz ML, Wiebringhaus P, Aitzetmueller M, 480
Hirsch T, Kueckelhaus M. Characteristics and Patient Reported Outcome Measures in Lipedema Patients—Establishing a Base- 481
line for Treatment Evaluation in a High-Volume Center. *J Clin Med.* 482
2022;11(10):2836. doi:10.3390/jcm11102836 483
484
16. Al-Wardat M, Clarke C, Alwardat N, Kassab M, Salimei C, 485
Gualtieri P, Marchetti M, Best T, Di Renzo L. The Difficulties in Emotional Regulation among a Cohort of Females with Lipedema. 486
Int J Environ Res Public Health. 2022;19(20):13679. 487
doi:10.3390/ijerph192013679 488
489
17. Kempa S, Gross M, Oliinyk D, Siegmund A, Müller M, Prantl L, 490
Tews HC. Health Implications of Lipedema: Analysis of Patient Questionnaires and Population-Based Matched Controls. 491
Life (Basel). 2024;14(3):295. doi:10.3390/life14030295 492
493
18. Falck J, Nygårdh A, Rolander B, Jonasson LL, Mårtensson J. 494
Dealing with lipoedema: women's experiences of healthcare, self-care, and treatments—a mixed-methods study. *BMC Womens* 495
Health. 2025;25:171. doi:10.1186/s12905-025-03659-6 496